

Experimental Analysis of the Mechanical Behaviour of Clay Masonry with Mortars Composed of Recycled Mortars

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Abstract. This work reports a part of research aiming at the development of sustainable masonry systems. The objective of this research is to study the influence of novel mortars with recycled aggregates on the mechanical behaviour of masonry wallets, with specific focus on the compressive behaviour. Four different types of general-purpose mortar and two different types of clay units were used to construct the specimens according to EN 1052-1:1999 standard, building up 8 combinations. In total, 32 specimens (4 specimens per combination) were tested to determine the compressive strength and E-modulus. All the specimens were built and tested at the R&D laboratory of Wienerberger in Beerse (B) using standard test machine with a loading capacity of 2500 KN. In all cases, the specimens made with mortars having recycled aggregates indicated a comparable compressive strength (higher by 10% in general) having a lower E-modulus (by around 50% in general) comparing to the specimens made with commercial mortars.

Testing matrix

Two types of aggregates, namely commercial sand (denoted by S in this document) and the recycled aggregates, developed within the SUBLime ITN network [1], (denoted by R) were used to make the mortar mixes which included 1:5 cement and 1:1:6 cement-lime mortars. Regarding the masonry units, two different types of clay bricks were used: one facing solid brick titled Kassandra (K) and another vertically perforated brick called Thermobrick (T).

The specimens were built fulfilling the dimensional requirements of EN 1052-1 [2] European standard, i.e., the specimens with K bricks were with two bricks in width and six bricks in height while the ones with T bricks were two bricks in width and three bricks in height with a 10 mm of nominal thickness of the mortar joint. After the construction of the specimens, to protect them from drying out fast, they were covered with polythene sheets for the first three days, according to the recommendations of EN 1052-1 [2], then uncovered and left in the lab conditions until their testing age, 28 and 42 days for the specimens made with 1:5 and 1:1:6 mortars, respectively.

After rectifying the loading surfaces of the specimens with the same mortar mixes used to build them, to ensure the uniform distribution of the load, they were tested under a force control condition with a loading rate of 0.04 MPa/s. The first specimen of each group was tested under a constant load rate until failure to estimate the compressive strength of each group then the remaining three specimens of the group were tested following the loading protocol indicated in Fig. 1 in which the specimen is loaded up to 1/3 of its compressive strength (the linear behaviour range) and unloaded within three cycles of loading then loaded again up to the failure of the specimen. Simply, the compressive strength is derived from the

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maximum load applied to the specimen while the E-modulus is calculated based on the load-displacement variations during the second and third cycles, discarding the first cycle.

Fig. 1. The loading protocol used for the E-modulus test

Results

The results obtained from the tests for the compressive strength and E-modulus can be seen in Table 1, together with their E/compressive strength ratio.

Table 1. The results of compression tests

<i>Label of set</i>	<i>Compressive strength [CV%] MPa</i>	<i>E-modulus [CV%] MPa</i>	<i>E/f_c ratio [CV%] -</i>
<i>KI:5S</i>	10.1 [8%]	2679 [5%]	289 [5%]
<i>KI:5R</i>	11.4 [11%]	1593 [19%]	140 [15%]
<i>KI:1:6S</i>	11 [7%]	2697 [6%]	250 [1%]
<i>KI:1:6R</i>	12.3 [6%]	2328 [7%]	187 [12%]
<i>KI:1:6S</i>	4.2 [6%]	5590 [17%]	1281 [15%]
<i>KI:1:6R</i>	6.6 [10%]	3925 [22%]	586 [11%]
<i>KI:1:6S</i>	6 [16%]	3353 [8%]	603 [21%]
<i>KI:1:6R</i>	8.5 [8%]	3250 [15%]	384 [17%]

As can be seen, the compressive strength of the specimens made with mortars with recycled aggregates (R) are slightly higher than the ones with commercial (S) mortars for both case of Kassandra and Thermobricks. However, the E-modulus shows the opposite trend and the E-modulus of the R specimens are significantly lower than the S specimens.

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References

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